

**“Doing Justice! Doing Just This!
Understanding justice in
transdisciplinary and
transformative research”**

Event Report | LRN Summer School

28 – 29 June 2023

Leibniz Institute of
Ecological Urban and
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IMPRINT

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About "Leibniz Sustain"

The Leibniz Research Network "Knowledge for Sustainable Development" bundles and networks relevant research competencies in the Leibniz Association and contributes to the effectiveness and visibility of research for sustainable development. To this end, the network organises synthesis workshops, international conferences and summer schools in cooperation with other Leibniz institutions and external partners from science and practice, as well as future dialogues with influential personalities from politics, business and society.

To learn more about the network on its website: <https://www.leibniz-sustain.de/en>

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1 Introduction

The **Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER)** in Dresden, Germany, in collaboration with the Leibniz Research Network "Knowledge for Sustainable Development" **organised a two day early-career summer school**, for 27 participants, to reflect upon and deepen the understanding of justice as applied to **transdisciplinary and transformative research (TTR)**.

TTR seeks to address pressing and complex sustainability challenges by bringing together academic and societal partners. In doing so, TTR aims to co-produce new types of knowledge and transform the ways in which such knowledge is used in society. However, TTR might as well reproduce or create new social, economic, environmental and intersectional injustices if it lacks concepts and methods to reflect upon and address justice. If un-attended, justice implications may run the risk of ultimately exacerbating divides e.g. with-in or between species (non-/human), social groups (gender, class, ethnicity, religion, age, ability, etc.), urban and rural communities, or between the Global South and the Global North. Such challenges urge for reflexivity to acknowledge the bright and dark sides of transformations and to engage with the **concept of justice** and its implications for TTR. The summer school was guided by the following questions:

- **What are "just" transformations and how to enable them?**
- **How can TTR methods contribute to reflexivity and depth in terms of just transformations?**
- **How to ensure reciprocity and diversity in research processes in support of justice?**
- **How to define and apply ethical reflection criteria in the research process?**

Figure 1: Group photo of all the summer school participants. Source: IOER/ Anna-Maria Schielicke

2 Event programme

Day 1: Wednesday, June 28, 2023

8:30 – 9:00	Arrival and registration
9:00 – 9:30	Welcome Address (Marc Wolfram)
9:30 – 10:30	Introduction to the LRN Summer School (Franziska Ehnert, Neelakshi Joshi & Marina Novikova)
10:30 – 11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:00 – 12:30	Setting the Scene The (Un)Doings of Justice: Some Impossible, Insistent and Transitional Questions (Martin Savransky)
12:30 – 13:30	<i>Lunch break</i>
13:30 – 15:00	Committing to Justice Justice is in the details: Beyond aspirations and towards commitment in transdisciplinary and transformative research (Guido Caniglia)
15:00 – 15:30	<i>Coffee break</i>
15:30 – 17:30	Navigating terra incognita - Part 1: Reflection criteria for ethics and justice in TTR (Franziska Ehnert, Neelakshi Joshi & Marina Novikova)
18:00	Dinner with "The Food Bin" (Zur Tonne) in the Grand Garden

Day 2: Thursday, June 29, 2023

9:00 – 10:30	Locating Justice Confronting colonial modernities? Struggles for justice in a 'many worlds world' (Saurabh Arora)
10:30 – 11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:00 – 12:30	Navigating terra incognita - Part 2: Reflection criteria for ethics and justice in TTR (Franziska Ehnert, Neelakshi Joshi & Marina Novikova)
12:30 – 13:30	<i>Lunch break</i>
13:30 – 15:30	Arriving on the Scene: Conclusions (Franziska Ehnert, Neelakshi Joshi & Marina Novikova)
15:30 – 16:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
16:00 – 18:00	NESTing Space: dialogue and inspiration to move forward (Joint event with the NEST Conference)
19:00	Do-it- toGEtHer: An Evening for Creative Collaboration at GEH8 (Joint event with the NEST Conference)

3 Lectures

The two-day summer school was designed to include diverse theoretical inputs by three prominent lecturers:

Dr. Martin Savransky

[Associate Professor in the Department of Sociology at Goldsmiths, University of London, UK]

His input:

Figure 2: Dr. Martin Savransky interacting with participants. Source: IOER/ Anna-Maria Schielicke

The (Un)Doings of Justice: Some Impossible, Insistent and Transitional Questions

Martin Savransky's lecture delved into the elusive concept of justice, pondering its meaning and forms amidst the backdrop of colonial, capitalist, and extractive injustices that have shaped our world. He emphasized the impossibility of fully addressing these questions, acknowledging that while answers abound, they ultimately fall short in capturing the essence of justice. Despite the challenges, Dr. Savransky proposed that grappling with these unanswerable questions may offer valuable insights into the nature of justice, highlighting its persistent and transformative nature as an ongoing pursuit rather than a static achievement. In the opening session of the Summer School he devoted time to interrogating what the "just" in "just transitions" might

mean and what it might take. The critical questions posed and the discussion that followed suggested that rather than a state to be achieved (or a law to be enforced), justice insists rather than exists, it gets done but is never done with.

Dr. Dr. Guido Caniglia

[Scientific Director of the Konrad Lorenz Institute for Evolution and Cognition Research (KLI), Klosterneuburg, Austria]

His input:

Figure 3: Dr. Guido Caniglia presenting on navigating the complexities of justice. Source: IOER/ Anna-Maria Schielicke

Justice is in the details: Beyond aspirations and towards commitment in transdisciplinary and transformative research

In his input, Guido Caniglia stimulated reflection on the need to enable and empower researchers in TTR to ask and address the questions that emerge when committing to justice. The questions on how can one learn to acknowledge and leverage their own relative power and privilege and how does one make sense of the intersecting injustices in the processes they work in were central to his lecture. According to Dr. Dr. Caniglia, committing to and finding direction through justice are not things that we can say to possess but they are rather capacities that can be

cultivated, among others, through experience and reflexivity and through trial and error. In his lecture, he used the metaphor of navigation to offer an orientation and direction to the individual and collective journeys of early-career researchers.

Dr. Saurabh Arora

[Senior Lecturer in Technology and Innovation for Development (SPRU - Science Policy Research Unit), University of Sussex Business School, UK]

His input:

Figure 4: Dr. Saurabh Arora conducting an exercise on entanglements. Source: IOER/ Anna-Maria Schielicke

Confronting colonial modernities? Struggles for justice in a 'many worlds world'

In his input, Saurabh Arora reflected upon the fact that critical approaches often locate social and ecological injustices associated with sustainability challenges, in political formations of capitalism and economic growth. However, as he conveyed, temporally deeper and spatially wider political formations are currently neglected in frameworks for sustainability transformations. Amidst this neglect of globally hegemonic colonial modernities, sustainability scholars conceptualise justice in a wide variety of ways. Together with the Summer School participants, Dr. Aurora discussed two such framings from the 'just transitions' literature: socio-ecological

justice that counters modern nature-society divide while combining redistribution, recognition, and representation (Yaka 2019); and reparative justice for addressing past harms inflicted through settler-colonial violence (Williams and Steil 2022).

4 Workshops

The lectures were punctuated by group work sessions where the participants progressively worked towards developing reflection criteria and guiding questions for ethics and justice in TTR. The workshop started with a brainwriting exercise to generate ideas on doing justice in TTR, which were refined through group discussions. In order to enhance reflexivity in transdisciplinary research practice, the findings of the workshops suggest several guiding questions. Doing justice in TTR requires expectations to be made transparent, reflecting on what can be promised and what are limitations. It asks for a critical reading of definitions of (in)justice and for overcoming colonial understandings of justice. It emphasizes the need for an effective on-going evaluation in the sense of reflexive monitoring in action. It asks to reflect on power asymmetries and vulnerabilities in transdisciplinary collaborations. Developing empathy includes questions on what the limits of knowing one another's worldviews and epistemologies are. Regarding variegated forms of agency, it asks how to integrate non-human actors and nature as well as future generations into research processes. It asks for a culture of care and the creation of safe spaces, which encourage trust building and learning-by-failing.

Figure 5: Participants presenting reflection criteria for justice in TTR. Source: Neelakshi Joshi/IOER

Figure 6: Participants' group work on creating reflection criteria for ethics and justice in TTR.
 Source: IOER/ Anna-Maria Schielicke

5 Feedback

The feedback provided by the participants was overwhelmingly positive. The diverse nature of the event was highlighted as enriching and worthwhile. Participants particularly appreciated an open space to explore the idea of justice as well as to meet with like-minded researchers. One participant mentioned:

"The lectures were inspiring and provided a helpful mix of different aspects that were thought-provoking. Also, all of them had participatory elements that strengthened team-building".

The readings and group writing exercise were particularly well-received, with the group work being described as a useful activity. The organization of the program, the venue, and the atmosphere were praised, with specific mention of the joint event with Zur Tonne. Participants appreciated the ample opportunities for networking and social activities, such as food preparation in the park, which contributed to a welcoming and integrated atmosphere, as articulated by one participant:

"Mix of participants, organization of the program, the venue. The atmosphere was very good. Interesting people for networking and exchange".

Participants also provided some constructive feedback. One participant felt that the group work could have been more focused on concrete case studies rather than abstract tasks, and suggested having speakers together in a panel or interactive sessions to bring together different perspectives. Multiple participants felt that the summer school was too short for such a complex topic and missed more practical implications for their own research, as articulated here:

"The summer school was too short especially for such a complex topic. While it was great to have the opportunity to reflect upon concepts and theory, I missed more practical implications for my own research. Otherwise, thanks again for the organization and all the work you put into the summer school!"

Future events should consider mixing theoretical input with real case studies as well as planning for 3-4 days duration.

The organising team and some participants are continuing to work together to prepare a living document on the multiple understandings of justice and how to practice justice in TTR.

6 Reading list

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